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Work Package 7

Data interoperability and data sharing

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Executive Summary

The HEAP (Human Exposome Assessment Platform) is a Horizon 2020 project aimed at creating a technical research platform for assessing the impact of the exposome on human health. This platform will integrate data from six research cohorts and provide access to high-quality exposome data for the scientific community, policymakers, and healthcare stakeholders. The catalogue deliverable will serve as a comprehensive documentation of the various datasets, their structure, metadata, and their compliance with FAIR principles (Findable, Accessible, Interoperable, and Reusable). This document outlines the data management, interoperability strategies, ethical considerations, and technical resources dedicated to making the HEAP data widely accessible and reusable.

This deliverable

- Describe the data sources, their formats, and how they are collected, processed, and stored.
- Ensure compliance with European data protection regulations.
- Provide data access, sharing, and reuse mechanisms while maintaining security and privacy standards.
- Foster collaboration and interoperability within the European Open Science Cloud (EOSC) and other platforms.

The catalogue will be a foundational document for data stewards, researchers, and policymakers, ensuring that the HEAP data repository is comprehensive, accessible, and aligned with international standards.

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List of Abbreviations

API	Application Programming Interfaces
BBMRI	Biobanking and BioMolecular resources Research Infrastructure
BIBBOX	Basic Infrastructure Building Box
CON	Consumer Cohort
CSC	IT Center for Science, Finland
CSC	Cervical Screening Cohort
DOI	Digital Object Identifier
EHEN	THE EUROPEAN HUMAN EXPOSOME NETWORK
ELIXIR	European Life Sciences Infrastructure
FAIR	Findable, Accessible, Interoperable, and Reusable
FDP	FAIR data point
FMC	Finish Maternity Cohort
HEAP	HUMAN EXPOSOME ASSESSMENT PLATFORM
HPV	human papillomavirus
HPV	HPV vaccination cohort
KI	Karolinska Institutet
LSC	TirolGESUND Lifestyle Atlas

MAT	Maternity Cohort
MIABIS	Minimum Information About Blobank data Sharing
Molgenis	Molgenis is a collaborative open-source project on a mission to generate excellent software infrastructure for life science research.
OAI-PMH	Open Archives Initiative Protocol for Metadata Harvesting
OBO	Open Biological and Biomedical Ontology Foundry
OULU	University of Oulu, Finland
PID	Persistent Identifier
PI	Principal Investigator
STD	Sexually transmitted disease
SSI	Statens Serum Institut
UIBK	University of Innsbruck, Austria
WDC	Wearable Data Collection Study

1 Introduction

The HEAP project (Human Exposome Assessment Platform) aims to enable global collaborative exposome research by developing a comprehensive technical platform. This platform supports integrating, managing, and analysing diverse datasets, such as those collected from population cohorts and wearable sensors, to understand better the effects of internal and external environmental factors (the exposome) on human health. Data management and interoperability are fundamental to this effort because exposome research involves dealing with complex, heterogeneous data that require standardised methods for efficient sharing and analysis across multiple research domains and institutions. To support these, a catalogue is essential for

- Improved Data Discovery and Access: A well-structured catalogue allows researchers to easily find and access relevant datasets, promoting faster scientific discoveries.
- Enhanced Data Reusability: Standardised metadata and documentation ensure that datasets are interpretable and reusable by other researchers, adhering to FAIR (Findable, Accessible, Interoperable, Reusable) principles.
- Support for Data Integration: A comprehensive catalogue enables the seamless integration of heterogeneous datasets from multiple sources, facilitating holistic analysis of the exposome's impact on health.
- Increased Research Transparency: A good catalogue improves research transparency by providing clear descriptions and provenance of datasets, enabling reproducibility and validation of results.
- Facilitating Collaboration: A centralised catalogue supports collaboration by providing a common resource for sharing and accessing data across different research teams and institutions.

The main sections of this deliverable describe the project's sustainable cohorts, which are the main source of knowledge in the HEAP project. This deliverable describes the main purpose of an online data catalogue to make metadata about the HEAP Information Commons and Data & Feature warehouse available to stakeholders and the general public.

2 HEAP Cohorts

The overall goal of HEAP is to enable global collaborative exposome research towards cost-effective health interventions. HEAP will provide a system for obtaining, managing, sharing and analysing exposome data. Large-scale, comprehensive, population-based systems will be exploited to build sustainable systems for measuring the human exposome and its impact on health. The HEAP consortium will launch innovative scientific analysis methods beyond state-of-the-science technologies, high throughput epigenomics and metagenomics methods, computation resources, wearable exposome sensors, and applied Artificial Intelligence (Müller et al., 2020 – updated 2023).

HEAP will create a standardised, integrated, and generic informatics platform that will enable the creation of collaborative networks for the joint production of consistent and actionable knowledge to tackle the effects of exposome on health and society.

Data will be generated in 6 research sub-projects (Müller et al., 2020 – updated 2023):

1. HEAP - Cervical screening Cohort
2. HEAP - Maternity Cohort
3. HEAP - HPV vaccination Cohort
4. HEAP - My purchases Cohort
5. HEAP - Wearable Data Collection Study
6. HEAP - TirolGESUND Lifestyle Atlas

2.1 HEAP - Cervical screening Cohort

Leading partner (PI): KI, Joakim Dillner

The primary purpose of cervical screening is to screen all women between 23 and 70 to prevent the occurrence of invasive cervical cancer by detecting and removing precancerous lesions, which, if left untreated, could develop into invasive cervical cancer. As a result, the cervical screening program has provided samples to the National Clinical Cytology Biobank corresponding to around 670 000 unique women (updated 2024). Data is collected from the samples taken in the organised cervical screening program in Stockholm region, the capital region of Sweden, and national health registers and quality register databases.

The cervical screening cohort will provide samples from healthy tissue, pre-neoplastic lesions and cancer. The sequencing analysis of specimens, together with metadata, aims to identify and characterise risk factors that may impact the risk of having the disease or being healthy. The results will help citizens understand the risk factors that increase the risk of cancer and other diseases.

2.2 HEAP - Maternity Cohort

Leading partner (PI): UOULU, Ville Pimenoff, Heljä-Marja Surcel; KI/FICAN-MID, Matti Lehtinen.

The HEAP Maternity cohort establishes a population-based cohort biobank. The data collected is of calendar time and over generations. Hence, the relation to HEAP understands the exposome in this context over time and over generations.

The baseline cohort data for approx. 1.000.000 healthy participants consist of consented participation data. Registry linkage will be done by the original data provider only, and anonymous data (not pseudo-anonymised) will be delivered. The origin of the data is the Finnish National prenatal screening, with additional FMC screening results (HIV, syphilis, hepatitis B, rubella). CSC will provide data through controlled access after approval of data owner(s). The results will help citizens understand the risk factors that increase the risk of cancer and other diseases.

2.3 HEAP - HPV vaccination Cohort

Leading partner (PI): KI/FICAN-MID, Ville Pimenoff and Matti Lehtinen.

The HEAP HPV vaccination cohort aims to establish a randomised stratified intervention cohort. In this context, the exposome is related to the impact of exposure to health interventions over time.

The baseline data for 60.000 healthy participants consists of participating cohort data. Registry linkage will be done by the original data provider only, and anonymous data (not pseudo-anonymised) will be delivered.

All data collected come from an Intervention trial follow-up, with additional STD follow-up results (cytology, HPV and chlamydia) available. CSC will provide data through controlled access after the approval of the data owner(s). A subset of the sample will be used to generate microbiome metagenomic data. The expected size for the baseline data is in the gigabyte range, and for the sequence data, it is in the terabyte range.

The results will help citizens understand the risk factors that increase the risk of cancer and other diseases.

2.4 HEAP - Consumer cohort - My purchases Cohort

Leading partner (PI): SSI, Frederik Trier Møller

The HEAP Consumer cohort aims to use consumer purchase data to continuously model and assess the impact of household-consumed exposomes on health. The aim is to identify

purchases that may impact health and provide input to an efficient platform for handling and analysing large amounts of data on environmental exposures and their health effects.

Data is collected from commercial digital receipt providers (such as start-up company Storebox) and, if possible, loyalty programmes (such as COOP, pending approval). The data is reused from other sources, such as Danish registers, quality databases, research projects, digital receipt solutions, and loyalty programs.

The results will help citizens identify and avoid products that increase the risk of one or more diseases.

2.5 HEAP - Wearable Data Collection Study

Leading partner (PI): KI, Michael Snyder; KI/UOULU, Ville Pimenoff.

The HEAP wearable device study aims to establish a proof-of-concept study for monitoring biological and chemical environmental exposures (i.e. exposome) during pregnancy. The environmental data is collected during HEAP with a research plan approved by the scientific ethics committee at the University of Oulu (Finland, PI Ville Pimenoff). The project aims to demonstrate if biological and chemical exposomes can be monitored during pregnancy with longitudinal sampling over several months. The objective is to monitor exposures in pregnant women in relation to healthy childbearing and produce continuous personal exposome profiling of the participants.

All wearable device data is collected for the approved research plan during HEAP to recruit 100 pregnant/non-pregnant women for a pilot investigation on how the exposome may influence pregnancy and human health in general. The pilot will follow these 100 women to investigate how the exposome influences the mother's health. Participants are asked to wear the device to monitor their personal exposures for four months. Samples will be collected by the participant at two-week intervals and stored temporarily in a -20 degrees freezer holder before being delivered to the lab. Then, they will be stored in a -80 degrees freezer monthly. The samples will be collected and sent to the lab monthly.

The pilot study monitors multiple exposures and health measurements from wearable sensors that collect airborne biological and chemical particulate matter and toxic substances such as toxins, viruses, bacteria, fungal spores, animal debris, and plant pollens. This solution will provide progress towards personal exposome profiling and agnostic identification of environmental risk factors.

CSC will provide the non-sensitive part of the dataset through controlled access after the approval of the data owners and data access committee.

2.6 HEAP - Lifestyle Cohort - TirolGESUND Lifestyle Atlas

The main aim of the HEAP Lifestyle cohort within the TirolGESUND study (NCT05678426) is to investigate dynamics in DNA methylation risk signatures associated with ageing and women's cancers in the presence of non-pharmacological disease-preventing interventions.

Specifically, the effect of two lifestyle changes, smoking cessation or interval fasting with/without ketogenic dietary supplementation, in addition to guided, targeted exercise, will be evaluated over an intervention period of 6 months. Several biological samples that may act as surrogate samples for tissues at risk of (age-related) disease will be collected at baseline and every two months for 6 months. Optionally, biological samples will be collected at 12 and 18 months after initiation of the intervention. The study results in the TirolGESUND Lifestyle atlas will inform future preventive intervention studies.

All data originate from measurements derived from biological specimens collected, clinical observations made, or fitness tracker devices worn by participants within the TirolGESUND study. Following the initial publication of the study data, DNA methylation data and other clinical data will be deposited in a secure controlled access repository (European Genome-Phenome Archive).

The cohort comprises methylation and other omic data from > 3,000 samples from 156 women (>3 samples per visit, 4 visits).

The results from this study will help citizens understand factors decreasing the risk of cancer or other age-related diseases, that individual factors play a crucial role in cancer development, and that individual risk prediction may be an option supporting cancer prevention in the future.

3 Governance and Data Stewardship

Data governance and stewardship are critical in ensuring data integrity, quality, and compliance throughout the project's lifecycle and beyond. This section describes how data was initially sourced, how data editing and stewardship were organised, and how metadata updates were handled. This is for all six cohorts from the HEAP project, as well as recent metadata updates in the internal and EHEN catalogues.

3.1 Initial Data Acquisition and Management

The data used in the HEAP project is derived from six key cohorts, each addressing a specific aspect of public health and biomedical research. These cohorts include the Cervical Screening Cohort, Maternity Cohort, HPV Vaccination Cohort, Consumer Cohort, Wearable Data Collection Study, and Lifestyle Cohort. For each of these cohorts, detailed cohort papers have been planned, and some have already been published, outlining the data collection process, methodologies, and protocols in greater detail. These cohort papers are valuable resources because they allow researchers inside and outside the HEAP project to cite them when referencing or discussing specific datasets.

- HEAP - Cervical Screening Cohort: This cohort focuses on individuals participating in cervical cancer screening programs, collecting data on screening outcomes and follow-up care (Dillner et al., 2024).
- HEAP - Maternity Cohort: This cohort enables population-level estimation of exposures associated with disease development that may affect the mother or the child (Müller et al., 2020 – updated 2023).
- HEAP - HPV Vaccination Cohort: This cohort tracks individuals who have received HPV vaccinations, examining vaccine uptake, coverage, and long-term health impacts (Pimenoff et al., 2023).
- HEAP - My purchases cohort: This group focuses on general consumer health behaviour, analysing lifestyle choices, nutrition, and related factors (Møller et al., 2023).
- HEAP - Wearable Data Collection Study: This cohort involves data collected through wearable devices, providing longitudinal insights into personal biological and chemical exposure patterns (Müller et al., 2020 – updated 2023).
- HEAP - TirolGESUND Lifestyle Atlas: The focus here is on lifestyle choices, including smoking and other health-related behaviours (Müller et al., 2020 – updated 2023).

Each cohort was integrated into the catalogue using the Molgenis EMX2, with the goal of a consistent data structure and harmonisation across all cohorts. Furthermore, the FAIR (Findable, Accessible, Interoperable, and Reusable) principles were important in promoting transparency and long-term reuse.

These cohort papers serve as a valuable reference point, ensuring data users understand each dataset's context and methodologies. Researchers are encouraged to cite the relevant cohort paper whenever they use or discuss specific datasets, ensuring proper attribution and improving research reproducibility.

3.2 Data Editing and Stewardship Organization

Data stewardship was structured to ensure the accuracy, security, and accessibility of the collected data. Marker papers were used as primary references to determine the data parameters and methodologies used across cohorts. These publications served as benchmarks for data collection protocols, ensuring consistency and compliance with research standards.

3.3 Metadata Updates and Catalogue Management

The internal and [EHEN catalogues](#) ("HEAP," n.d.) have recently been updated with metadata for all six HEAP cohorts. These updates were critical for ensuring the datasets' integrity and accuracy as new information became available. Metadata edits included:

- **Correction of cohort assignments:** One cohort, which was incorrectly assigned to the HEAP project in the EHEN catalogue, was removed to ensure the accuracy of project-related data.
- **Refinement of cohort definitions:** The metadata was updated according to the current state of each cohort, particularly in, e.g. the name of the cohort, number of participants, inclusion criteria, the end year of the study, as well as data access conditions and linkage options.

The EHEN catalogue is separated into cohorts, variables, and networks; see Figure 1: Structure of the Catalogue.

New catalogue design we'd love to get your feedback at info@molgenis.org ([previous version](#))

EHEN

Welcome to the catalogue of **EHEN**: European Human Exposome Network. Select one of the content categories listed below.

COHORTS

73

Cohorts & Biobanks

COHORTS

VARIABLES

1860

Harmonised variables

VARIABLES

NETWORKS

9

Networks & Consortia

NETWORKS

4.131.293 Participants

The cumulative number of participants of all (sub)cohorts combined.

1.794.966 Samples

The cumulative number of participants with samples collected of all (sub)cohorts combined

Longitudinal 53%

Percentage of longitudinal datasets. The remaining datasets are cross-sectional.

This database was created using [MOLGENIS.org](#) ([github](#)).

Please cite [Swertz & Gini \(2022\)](#), [Van der Velde et al \(2018\)](#) or [Swertz et al \(2010\)](#) on use.

Software version: v10.103.1

Figure 1: Structure of the Catalogue

3.3.1 Networks

Within the EHEN are listed 9 networks, among others, the HEAP- Human Exposome Assessment Platform. The page lists a description, contact information, contributors, and the various cohorts that are part of HEAP; see Figure 2.

The screenshot shows the 'HEAP' page on the EHEN NETWORKS site. The page title is 'HEAP' with the subtitle 'Human exposome assessment platform'. A navigation menu on the left includes 'Description', 'Contact & Contributors', and 'Cohorts'. The 'DESCRIPTION' section states that the HEAP project provides an informatics platform for handling and analysing large amounts of data on environmental exposures and their health effects. The 'CONTACT AND CONTRIBUTORS' section lists six contributors in a 2x3 grid:

<p>prof. JD (Joakim) Dillner joakim.dillner@regionstockholm.se</p>	<p>ir. SNK (Sara) Nordqvist Kleppe sara.nordqvist.kleppe@ki.se</p>
<p>dr. SAM (Sara) Arroyo Mühr sara.arroyo.muhr@ki.se</p>	<p>dr. FTM (Frederik) Trier Møller frtm@ssi.dk</p>
<p>dr. TE (Tiina) Eriksson tiina.eriksson@tuni.fi</p>	<p>dr. VNP (Ville) Pimenoff ville.pimenoff@ki.se</p>

Figure 2: Overview of all cohorts

The 6 cohorts of the HEAP projects can also be found under the point Cohorts within the EHEN setting. The cohorts are listed alphabetically.

The representation of a cohort is structured as follows:

- Description
- General Design
- Population
- Contributors
- Subpopulations
- Networks
- Access Conditions
- Funding & Acknowledgements

The following figures show screenshots from the different cohorts.

New catalogue design we'd love to get your feedback at info@molgenis.org (previous version)

European Human Exposome **NETWORK**

OVERVIEW COHORTS NETWORKS ABOUT MORE ▾

EHEN > COHORTS

CON

My purchases cohort

<https://mineindkob.ssi.dk/> **CONTACT**

DESCRIPTION

This project aims to investigate how what we buy, and thus our diet, affects health, by analyzing purchase patterns and health information over time.

GENERAL DESIGN

Cohort type	Population cohort, Registry
Design	Longitudinal ⓘ
Collection type	Retrospective, Prospective
Start/End year	2021 - 2041
PID	CON

POPULATION

Countries	Denmark
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Figure 3: Extract from the "My purchases Cohort"

EHEN > COHORTS

CSC

Cervical screening cohort

CSC

- Description
- General Design
- Population
- Contributors
- Subpopulations
- Datasets
- Networks
- Access Conditions
- Funding & Acknowledgements

<https://nkcx.se>
CONTACT

DESCRIPTION

Cervical screening cohort comprising all women resident in Sweden aged 23-70 that are screened for human papillomavirus or cervical abnormalities.

GENERAL DESIGN

Cohort type	Population cohort, Registry, Biobank
Design	Longitudinal ↻
Collection type	Retrospective, Prospective
Start/End year	1964 - ongoing
PID	CSC

POPULATION

Countries	Sweden
Number of participants	670000
Number of participants with samples	670000
Population age groups	Young adult (18-24 years), Adult (25-44 years), Middle-aged (45-64 years), Aged (65-79 years)

Figure 4: Section from the "Cervical screening Cohort"

T6

- Description
- General Design
- Population
- Contributors
- Subpopulations
- Networks
- Access Conditions
- Funding & Acknowledgements

POPULATION

Countries	Austria
Number of participants	156
Number of participants with samples	156
Population age groups	Adult (25-44 years), Middle-aged (45-64 years)
Inclusion criteria	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> BMI range inclusion criterion ⓘ Clinically relevant lifestyle inclusion criterion ⓘ Age group inclusion criterion ⓘ

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SUBPOPULATIONS

List of subcohorts or subpopulations for this resource

Name	Description	Number of participants
Intermittent fasting with ketogenic supplement		→
Intermittent fasting without		→

Figure 5: Section from the depiction of the "TirolGESUND Lifestyle Atlas"

3.4 Long-term Data Stewardship and Sustainability

A decentralised approach is being planned to ensure the long-term sustainability and proper stewardship of HEAP project data. Each cohort representative will be granted access to the catalogue's staging area, allowing them to update information about their specific cohort promptly and accurately. This method enables cohort managers to keep up-to-date metadata and data entries, resulting in a more dynamic and responsive data management system.

To make this possible, a hands-on workshop is planned to train cohort representatives on how the catalogue is structured, how data can be updated, and best practices for data integrity.

The workshop will provide practical, step-by-step instructions to ensure each representative can navigate the Molgenis EMX2 platform and update data.

This strategy allows for timely updates and ensures that each cohort's data is accurate, relevant, and aligned with the project's overall data governance framework. The project aims to maintain high-quality data stewardship by providing ongoing access and training, ensuring that the catalogue remains a valuable resource for the scientific community long after the project's active phase.

4 Technical Infrastructure

This section describes how the catalogue was implemented in the beginning, evolved over the project lifetime and what the sustainability of the catalogue will be.

4.1 *Implementation of the Catalogue*

The development of the catalogue infrastructure began with the deployment of a Molgenis test instance within the BIBBOX framework. This setup was chosen for its modularity and ability to support the project's evolving data management requirements. Molgenis provided a solid platform for systematically collecting, organising, and validating cohort metadata, ensuring the infrastructure was scalable and adaptable as the project grew.

A critical aspect of this phase was working directly with cohort researchers to collect detailed metadata. To collect comprehensive cohort data, we provided targeted guidance on using FAIR (Findable, Accessible, Interoperable, and Reusable) data management principles. This involved giving researchers personalised advice on metadata standards, data harmonisation methodologies, and best practices for ensuring their data's long-term sustainability and usability.

In addition to metadata collection, there was a strong emphasis on harmonising data across cohorts to ensure consistency and compatibility. By aligning the cohort metadata with FAIR principles, we ensured that the data infrastructure met international standards while also being optimised for future interoperability and reuse. This approach laid the groundwork for a long-term and scalable catalogue that facilitates advanced data sharing and collaboration within the research community.

4.2 *Local Catalogue at Medical University Graz*

The BIBBOX (Basic Infrastructure Building Box) framework (Müller et al. 2023) is a pivotal component of the technical infrastructure development of the HEAP catalogue at the Medical University Graz. Initially created within the framework of the B3Africa project, BIBBOX provides a platform that enables the easy installation, deployment, and integration of open-source software solutions. It explicitly supports biomedical informatics and biobanking by offering a structured and scalable environment where various tools, referred to as apps, can be installed and managed.

BIBBOX is intended to follow the FAIR data principles (Findable, Accessible, Interoperable, and Reusable), which are critical for improving data quality and sharing in life sciences research. The platform helps researchers by making publishing datasets and associated software easier in a FAIR-compliant format. A key feature of BIBBOX is its modular architecture, which is built

on Docker containers. This enables rapid deployment and dependable execution across multiple computing environments, making it a versatile and adaptable solution for several research requirements.

The core components of BIBBOX include the BIBBOX Portal, Master FAIR Data Point (FDP) and the apps (see Table 1).

Table 1: Overview of the core BIBBOX components

BIBBOX Component	Description
BIBBOX Portal	A user-friendly web interface includes an app Store for installing various open-source apps and an app Instances section that shows all current installations.
Master FAIR Data Point (FDP)	This acts as a central hub, ensuring that all FAIRified apps follow the FAIR principles by exposing their metadata and datasets in a compliant manner. The FDP component ensures that external systems and researchers can easily find, access, and reuse data.
Apps	Each app is encapsulated within a Docker container and is intended to perform specific tasks. Some apps handle data and are advised to be FAIRified by including an FDP. The modularity of the BIBBOX architecture enables the simple integration of new software tools as the research environment evolves.

A test instance of the catalogue was hosted using the BIBBOX framework throughout the project, which provided a secure and scalable solution for managing and sharing biomedical data. The BIBBOX architecture's flexibility allowed for adding new datasets and services to the catalogue as the project progressed, ensuring that the platform was up to date with the most recent scientific tools and standards. This allowed for quick testing and seamless movement between the testing area and productive catalogue as the version and design of the productive system could be easily mirrored using the BIBBOX framework.

The local catalogue at the Medical University Graz is primarily intended for prototyping and testing. It enables us and other researchers to experiment with data management tools, workflows, and services on Molgenis EMX2, a versatile platform designed specifically for life sciences data management. This local environment enables the testing of various biomedical datasets, ensuring that workflows are thoroughly refined before moving on to the final production-level catalogue at EHEN (European Human Exposome Network).

Once the prototyping and testing phases were completed, validated data and services were moved to the production-level catalogue hosted by EHEN. Molgenis EMX2 has been used to implement the local and production catalogues, ensuring a seamless transition. EHEN's production catalogue is intended for long-term sustainability and broader access, guaranteeing that datasets meet stringent data quality, security, and compliance standards, including adherence to the FAIR principles (Findable, Accessible, Interoperable, and Reusable).

Therefore, we have a dual-catalogue system: ❶ a local for prototyping and ❷ EHEN for production.

This dual-catalogue system provides flexibility during development while ensuring that only the most tested and secure data and workflows are added to the production-level catalogue. This ensures the final system is robust and long-lasting, allowing the scientific community to continue using it.

4.2.1 Molgenis EMX2 at EHEN Catalogue

MOLGENIS EMX2 is a powerful open-source platform designed to simplify managing, analysing, and sharing complex scientific data, particularly in life sciences, biomedical research, and personalised medicine. Developed as part of the MOLGENIS suite, EMX2 is the enhanced version of the original EMX (Entity Model eXtender) data model, providing greater flexibility, scalability, and ease of use. The platform offers an intuitive interface and a robust backend for storing large datasets, managing metadata, and ensuring data interoperability across various research projects and infrastructures.

At its core, MOLGENIS EMX2 is a metadata-driven system that allows researchers to define their data structures and manage them to support FAIR principles (Findable, Accessible, Interoperable, and Reusable). It is particularly suited for cohort studies, biobanking, genomics, and exposome research, where complex data types and relationships between entities (samples, individuals, measurements, etc.) need to be meticulously tracked and managed.

Key Features of MOLGENIS EMX2:

1. **Flexible Data Modelling:** EMX2 enables users to define and modify their data models using schema language that allows for the creation of custom entities, attributes, and relationships between them. This makes it ideal for handling diverse datasets in a wide range of scientific disciplines.
2. **FAIR Data Management:** EMX2 is designed with FAIR principles in mind, providing comprehensive tools to ensure that data is well-structured, properly annotated, and easily discoverable. Researchers can define metadata standards, assign unique identifiers, and make data accessible through open standards and APIs.
3. **Interoperability:** MOLGENIS EMX2 supports integrating data from various sources and ensures that the data remains interoperable with other systems and platforms. It is compatible with popular ontologies and metadata standards, facilitating cross-disciplinary research and data sharing.
4. **User-Friendly Interface:** The platform offers an intuitive web interface that simplifies the management of large datasets. Users can import, view, and query data without extensive technical expertise, making the platform accessible to researchers and data stewards alike.
5. **Scalability and Performance:** EMX2 is built to handle the growing needs of large-scale research projects. It can scale to accommodate extensive datasets, ensuring optimal performance even as data complexity increases.
6. **Integration with Analytical Tools:** MOLGENIS EMX2 can be integrated with various bioinformatics tools and platforms for analysis, visualisation, and reporting. This makes it a versatile platform for end-to-end data management, from data collection to downstream analysis.

MOLGENIS EMX2 has been adopted by several large research consortia and projects, including BBMRI (Biobanking and BioMolecular Resources Research Infrastructure) and ELIXIR, demonstrating its effectiveness in managing large, diverse datasets while adhering to high standards of data stewardship and interoperability.

Especially when looking at cohort catalogues, MOLGENIS supports the following six aspects:

1. Metadata Management for Catalogues

- **Flexible Data Models:** MOLGENIS EMX2 allows researchers to create custom data models that define the entities, attributes, and relationships specific to their catalogue. This enables precise representation of complex datasets, such as biological samples, research cohorts, and study metadata.
- **Metadata Annotations:** Each entity in the catalogue can be richly annotated with metadata, making it easier to organise and describe datasets in a way that is both

human-readable and machine-readable. These annotations enhance the ability to harvest and query data efficiently.

2. FAIR Principles for Catalogue Data

- **Findability:** MOLGENIS ensures that catalogue data is discoverable by assigning persistent identifiers (PIDs) to datasets and entities. It supports metadata standards that enable external systems to search and locate relevant data. The system can generate searchable catalogue entries with appropriate metadata for public and internal use.
- **Accessibility:** Data in MOLGENIS catalogues can be made accessible via secure APIs and user-friendly web interfaces. This ensures that catalogue data can be harvested or queried by external systems or users in a controlled manner, supporting access policies and user permissions.
- **Interoperability:** MOLGENIS catalogues are built on widely accepted standards and can integrate with various ontologies (such as MIABIS, OBO Foundry ontologies, etc.). This promotes interoperability, allowing the catalogue data to be harvested and combined with other datasets using common vocabularies and metadata structures.
- **Reusability:** The system supports data licensing information, enabling users to specify reuse conditions. This helps external systems understand how catalogue data can be accessed and reused, ensuring compliance with legal and ethical frameworks.

3. Harvesting and Catalogue Integration

- **APIs for Data Harvesting:** MOLGENIS provides RESTful APIs that facilitate the automatic harvesting of catalogue data by external systems. These APIs allow other platforms or data repositories (such as the European Open Science Cloud or BBMRI catalogue) to access and retrieve up-to-date catalogue entries from MOLGENIS.
- **Support for OAI-PMH Protocol:** MOLGENIS can be configured to support the Open Archives Initiative Protocol for Metadata Harvesting (OAI-PMH). This protocol enables the systematic harvesting of metadata from the MOLGENIS catalogue by external aggregators or metadata repositories.
- **Federated catalogue Integration:** MOLGENIS supports the integration of federated catalogue data by allowing distributed catalogues to share metadata across platforms. This is particularly useful for research infrastructures that rely on decentralised data repositories, as MOLGENIS can harmonise metadata and facilitate cross-repository searches.
- **Syndication and Synchronisation of Catalogue Data:** MOLGENIS allows catalogue data to be syndicated to other platforms, keeping metadata in sync with external data repositories. This ensures that updates to catalogue entries are reflected across multiple systems, promoting consistency and reducing data silos.

4. Advanced Search and Query Mechanisms

- **Advanced Search:** MOLGENIS provides an intuitive search interface that enables users to query catalogue data using keywords, filters, and other criteria. This supports the internal data harvesting by users, making it easier to find relevant datasets within large catalogues.
- **SPARQL and Linked Data Support:** MOLGENIS can be configured to support SPARQL queries, enabling linked data harvesting. This capability is particularly useful for integrating with other linked data repositories and enabling semantic search across catalogue data.
- **Granular Data Access:** Catalogue entries in MOLGENIS can be accessed at various levels of granularity, from high-level metadata summaries to detailed records of individual entities. This supports different types of harvesting, from essential metadata harvesting to complete data retrieval.

5. Persistent Identifiers (PIDs) and Versioning

- **Support for Persistent Identifiers:** MOLGENIS integrates with systems like DOI (Digital Object Identifier) or handle to assign persistent identifiers to catalogue data. This ensures that catalogue entries are uniquely and permanently identifiable, making them easier to harvest and reference across systems.
- **Versioning Support:** MOLGENIS supports version control for catalogue data, allowing data stewards to manage different versions of datasets and metadata entries. This ensures that external systems harvesting catalogue data can access the correct version and maintain consistency across multiple catalogues.

6. Data Publishing and Sharing Tools

- **Public and Private Catalogues:** MOLGENIS allows the creation of both public and private catalogues, with configurable access controls for different user groups. Public catalogues can be exposed for harvesting by external systems, while authorised users or systems can access private catalogues.
- **Integration with Data Repositories:** MOLGENIS can be integrated with external data repositories, allowing catalogue data to be published and harvested by platforms like ELIXIR, BMMRI, or EOSC. This ensures that catalogue data can be shared widely and reused in other research contexts.

4.3 Future Maintenance of the Catalogue

Data regarding the various cohorts can be changed in the staging area of the EHEN Catalogue. The Molgenis support team can be contacted at support@molgenis.org to get [administrative rights and technical support](#).

Currently, the people responsible for the respective cohorts are as follows:

- HEAP - Cervical screening Cohort: Dr. Sara Arroyo Mühr, KI
- HEAP - Maternity Cohort: Dr. Ville Pimenoff, UOULU
- HEAP - HPV vaccination Cohort: Dr. Ville Pimenoff, UOULU
- HEAP - Wearable Data Collection Study: Dr. Ville Pimenoff, UOULU
- HEAP - My purchases Cohort: Dr. Frederik Trier Møller, SSI
- HEAP - TirolGESUND Lifestyle Atlas: Dr. Chiara Herzog, UIBK

5 Access Procedures

This section outlines the procedures for accessing the HEAP project's metadata and datasets, emphasising the criteria for general access, licensing requirements, and access to the metadata catalogue hosted on the EHEN platform.

5.1 General Access Criteria

Access to HEAP's data and metadata is structured to balance openness with the need to protect sensitive information. Researchers and collaborators seeking access to the data must comply with ethical guidelines and data protection regulations. Data requests are evaluated based on the researcher's affiliation, research purpose, and compliance with HEAP's governance policies. Additionally, researchers are expected to adhere to the HEAP data usage agreements to ensure the proper handling and sharing of data within the scientific community.

5.2 Data Access License

HEAP datasets are governed by a standardised Data Access License to ensure the proper use, sharing, and distribution of sensitive information. Licences are categorised based on the level of data sensitivity:

Open Data License: This licence applies to fully anonymised datasets, allowing them to be shared publicly to promote open collaboration. It also includes synthetic datasets generated to simulate real-world data without compromising privacy. These datasets are available for unrestricted use, fostering broad participation in research while ensuring that sensitive information remains protected.

Restricted Data License: This license applies to datasets containing sensitive or personal information. Approved researchers are granted access after obtaining ethical approval and signing data usage agreements. Researchers must apply for access to restricted data through the HEAP platform. Each application is reviewed for ethical compliance, and access is granted once the required conditions are met.

5.3 Access at the Metadata Level

The metadata catalogue, hosted on the EHEN platform, provides comprehensive descriptions of datasets from all HEAP cohorts. This catalogue is publicly accessible without login credentials, supporting transparency and fostering broader collaboration within the research community. Users can browse detailed metadata about cohort samples, variables, and methods used, allowing them to evaluate the relevance of the data to their research.

However, editing metadata is restricted to authorised users to ensure the accuracy and integrity of the information. Access to editing functions requires secure login via the Life Science Login/AAI system. This system integrates with institutional authentication, enabling researchers to use their institutional credentials for secure access. By allowing only verified users to modify or update the metadata, the system ensures that data integrity is maintained, protecting the quality of shared resources across the platform.

6 References

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7 Annexe

7.1 Data Model

The Heap metadata catalogue for a cohort consists of multiple interlinked tables (see Figure 6).

Figure 6: The Heap metadata catalogue data model schema for a cohort.

7.1.1 Catalogue Data Model

1. Publications

- `publication_id` (INT, PRIMARY KEY)
- `doi` (VARCHAR, NOT NULL)
- `title` (TEXT, NOT NULL)
- `authors` (STRING_ARRAY)
- `year` (INT)
- `journal` (VARCHAR)
- `volume` (INT)
- `number` (INT)
- `pagination` (VARCHAR)
- `publisher` (VARCHAR)
- `school` (VARCHAR)
- `abstract` (TEXT)
- `resources` (INT[], FOREIGN KEY to Extended resources)

2. Resources

- `resource_id` (INT, PRIMARY KEY)
- `overview_heading` (VARCHAR)
- `id` (INT, NOT NULL)
- `pid` (INT)
- `acronym` (VARCHAR)
- `name` (TEXT, NOT NULL)
- `website` (VARCHAR)
- `description` (TEXT)
- `contacts` (INT[], FOREIGN KEY to `Contacts`)

3. Version

- `version_id` (INT, PRIMARY KEY)
- `version_number` (VARCHAR)

4. Contacts

- `contact_id` (INT, PRIMARY KEY)
- `resource_id` (INT, FOREIGN KEY to Resources)
- `role_ids` (INT[], FOREIGN KEY to CatalogueOntologies)
- `first_name` (VARCHAR)
- `last_name` (VARCHAR)
- `prefix` (VARCHAR)

- **initials** (VARCHAR)
- **title_id** (INT, FOREIGN KEY to CatalogueOntologies)
- **organisation_id** (INT, FOREIGN KEY to SharedStaging.Organisations)
- **email** (VARCHAR)
- **orcid** (VARCHAR)
- **homepage** (VARCHAR)
- **photo** (FILE)
- **expertise** (TEXT)

5. Extended resources (Extends 'Resources')

- **resource_id** (INT, PRIMARY KEY)
- **lead_organisation_ids** (INT[], FOREIGN KEY to SharedStaging.Organisations)
- **additional_organisation_ids** (INT[], FOREIGN KEY to SharedStaging.Organisations)
- **external_identifiers** (INT[], FOREIGN KEY to External identifiers)
- **logo** (FILE)
- **countries** (INT[], FOREIGN KEY to CatalogueOntologies)
- **publications** (INT[], FOREIGN KEY to Publications)
- **funding_statement** (TEXT)
- **acknowledgements** (TEXT)
- **documentation** (INT[], FOREIGN KEY to Documentation)

6. Subcohorts

- **subcohort_id** (INT, PRIMARY KEY)
- **resource_id** (INT, FOREIGN KEY to Extended resources, NOT NULL)
- **name** (VARCHAR, NOT NULL)
- **description** (TEXT)
- **number_of_participants** (INT)
- **counts** (INT[], FOREIGN KEY to Subcohort counts)
- **inclusion_start** (INT)
- **inclusion_end** (INT)
- **age_groups** (INT[], FOREIGN KEY to CatalogueOntologies)
- **main_medical_condition** (INT[], FOREIGN KEY to CatalogueOntologies)
- **comorbidity** (INT[], FOREIGN KEY to CatalogueOntologies)
- **countries** (INT[], FOREIGN KEY to CatalogueOntologies)
- **regions** (INT[], FOREIGN KEY to CatalogueOntologies)
- **inclusion_criteria** (TEXT)
- **supplementary_information** (TEXT)

7. Collection events

- `collection_event_id` (INT, PRIMARY KEY)
- `resource_id` (INT, FOREIGN KEY to Extended resources)
- `name` (VARCHAR)
- `description` (TEXT)
- `subcohort_ids` (INT[], FOREIGN KEY to `Subcohorts`)
- `start_year_id` (INT, FOREIGN KEY to `CatalogueOntologies`)
- `start_month_id` (INT, FOREIGN KEY to `CatalogueOntologies`)
- `end_year_id` (INT, FOREIGN KEY to `CatalogueOntologies`, NULLABLE)
- `end_month_id` (INT, FOREIGN KEY to `CatalogueOntologies`, NULLABLE)
- `age_group_ids` (INT[], FOREIGN KEY to `CatalogueOntologies`)
- `number_of_participants` (INT)
- `areas_of_information_ids` (INT[], FOREIGN KEY to `CatalogueOntologies`)
- `data_category_ids` (INT[], FOREIGN KEY to `CatalogueOntologies`)
- `sample_category_ids` (INT[], FOREIGN KEY to `CatalogueOntologies`)
- `standardized_tool_ids` (INT[], FOREIGN KEY to `CatalogueOntologies`)
- `standardized_tools_other` (VARCHAR)
- `core_variables` (VARCHAR[], ARRAY)
- `supplementary_information` (TEXT)

8. Datasets

- `dataset_id` (INT, PRIMARY KEY)
- `resource_id` (INT, FOREIGN KEY to `Extended resources`, NOT NULL)
- `name` (VARCHAR, NOT NULL)
- `label` (VARCHAR)
- `since_version` (VARCHAR)
- `until_version` (VARCHAR)
- `unit_of_observation_id` (INT, FOREIGN KEY to `CatalogueOntologies`)
- `keywords` (INT[], FOREIGN KEY to `CatalogueOntologies`)
- `description` (TEXT)
- `number_of_rows` (INT)

9. External identifiers

- `external_identifier_id` (INT, PRIMARY KEY)
- `resource_id` (INT, FOREIGN KEY to `Extended resources`, NOT NULL)
- `identifier` (TEXT, NOT NULL)
- `external_identifier_type_id` (INT, FOREIGN KEY to `CatalogueOntologies`)
- `external_identifier_type_other` (TEXT)

10. Subcohort counts

- `subcohort_count_id` (INT, PRIMARY KEY)
- `subcohort_id` (INT, FOREIGN KEY to `Subcohorts`, NOT NULL)
- `age_group_id` (INT, FOREIGN KEY to `CatalogueOntologies`, NOT NULL)
- `N_total` (INT)
- `N_female` (INT)
- `N_male` (INT)

11. Data resources (Extends 'Extended Resource')

- `data_resource_id` (INT, PRIMARY KEY)
- `local_name` (VARCHAR)
- `keywords` (TEXT)
- `population_heading` (VARCHAR)
- `number_of_participants` (INT)
- `number_of_participants_with_samples` (INT)
- `regions` (INT[], FOREIGN KEY to `CatalogueOntologies`)
- `population_age_groups` (INT[], FOREIGN KEY to `CatalogueOntologies`)
- `population_disease` (INT[], FOREIGN KEY to `CatalogueOntologies`)
- `population_oncology_topology` (INT[], FOREIGN KEY to `CatalogueOntologies`)
- `population_oncology_morphology` (INT[], FOREIGN KEY to `CatalogueOntologies`)
- `contents_heading` (VARCHAR)
- `access_heading` (VARCHAR)
- `data_holder_id` (INT, FOREIGN KEY to `SharedStaging.Organisations`)
- `information_heading` (VARCHAR)
- `design_paper_ids` (INT[], FOREIGN KEY to `Publications`)
- `informed_consent_type_id` (INT, FOREIGN KEY to `CatalogueOntologies`)
- `supplementary_information` (TEXT)
- `collaborations_heading` (VARCHAR)

12. Documentation

- `documentation_id` (INT, PRIMARY KEY)
- `resource_id` (INT, FOREIGN KEY to `Extended resources`, NOT NULL)
- `name` (VARCHAR, NOT NULL)
- `type_id` (INT, FOREIGN KEY to `CatalogueOntologies`)
- `description` (TEXT)
- `url` (VARCHAR)
- `file` (FILE)

13. Cohorts (Extends 'Data resource')

- cohort_id (INT, PRIMARY KEY)
- contact_email (VARCHAR, NOT NULL)
- type_id (INT, FOREIGN KEY to CatalogueOntologies)
- type_other (VARCHAR)
- design_id (INT, FOREIGN KEY to CatalogueOntologies)
- design_description (TEXT)
- design_schematic (VARCHAR, file reference)
- collection_type_id (INT, FOREIGN KEY to CatalogueOntologies)
- inclusion_criteria_id (INT, FOREIGN KEY to CatalogueOntologies)
- other_inclusion_criteria (TEXT)
- start_year (INT)
- end_year (INT)
- subcohort_id (INT, FOREIGN KEY to Subcohorts)
- collection_event_id (INT, FOREIGN KEY to Collection events)
- release_type_id (INT, FOREIGN KEY to CatalogueOntologies)
- release_description (TEXT)
- linkage_options (TEXT)
- data_access_conditions_id (INT, FOREIGN KEY to CatalogueOntologies)
- data_use_conditions_id (INT, FOREIGN KEY to CatalogueOntologies)
- data_access_conditions_description (TEXT)
- data_access_fee (BOOLEAN)
- study_ids (INT[], FOREIGN KEY to Studies)
- network_ids (INT[], FOREIGN KEY to Networks)

14. Dataset mappings

- mapping_id (INT, PRIMARY KEY)
- source_id (INT, FOREIGN KEY to Extended resources, NOT NULL)
- source_dataset_id (INT, FOREIGN KEY to Datasets, NOT NULL)
- target_id (INT, FOREIGN KEY to Extended resources, NOT NULL)
- target_dataset_id (INT, FOREIGN KEY to Datasets, NOT NULL)
- order (INT)
- description (TEXT)
- syntax (TEXT)

7.1.2 Variables Data Model

1. Variable Mappings

- `variable_mapping_id` (INT, PRIMARY KEY)
- `source_id` (INT, FOREIGN KEY to `Extended resources`, NOT NULL)
- `source_dataset_id` (INT, FOREIGN KEY to `Datasets`, NOT NULL)
- `source_variable_ids` (INT[], FOREIGN KEY to All variables)
- `source_variables_other_datasets` (INT[], FOREIGN KEY to All variables)
- `target_id` (INT, FOREIGN KEY to `Extended resources`, NOT NULL)
- `target_dataset_id` (INT, FOREIGN KEY to `Datasets`, NOT NULL)
- `target_variable_id` (INT, FOREIGN KEY to `All variables`, NOT NULL)
- `match_id` (INT, FOREIGN KEY to `CatalogueOntologies`, NOT NULL)
- `status_id` (INT, FOREIGN KEY to `CatalogueOntologies`)
- `description` (TEXT)
- `syntax` (TEXT)
- `comments` (TEXT)

2. Variable Values

- `variable_value_id` (INT, PRIMARY KEY)
- `resource_id` (INT, FOREIGN KEY to `Extended resources`, NOT NULL)
- `variable_id` (INT, FOREIGN KEY to `Variables`, NOT NULL)
- `value` (VARCHAR, NOT NULL)
- `label` (VARCHAR)
- `order` (INT)
- `is_missing` (BOOLEAN)
- `ontology_term_URI` (VARCHAR)
- `since_version` (VARCHAR)
- `until_version` (VARCHAR)

3. Variables

- `variable_id` (INT, PRIMARY KEY)
- `format_id` (INT, FOREIGN KEY to `CatalogueOntologies`, NOT NULL)
- `unit_id` (INT, FOREIGN KEY to `CatalogueOntologies`)
- `references_id` (INT, FOREIGN KEY to All variables)
- `mandatory` (BOOLEAN)
- `description` (TEXT)
- `order` (INT)
- `example_values` (STRING_ARRAY)

- permitted_values (INT[], FOREIGN KEY to Variable values)
- keywords (INT[], FOREIGN KEY to CatalogueOntologies)
- repeats_id (INT, FOREIGN KEY to Repeated variables)
- vocabularies (INT[], FOREIGN KEY to CatalogueOntologies)
- notes (TEXT)

4. All variables

- variable_id (INT, PRIMARY KEY)
- resource_id (INT, FOREIGN KEY to Extended resources)
- dataset_id (INT, FOREIGN KEY to Datasets)
- name (VARCHAR, NOT NULL, UNIQUE)
- label (VARCHAR)
- collection_event_id (INT, FOREIGN KEY to Collection events)
- since_version (VARCHAR)
- until_version (VARCHAR)
- mapping_id (INT, FOREIGN KEY to Variable mappings)

5. Repeated variables (Extends 'All variables')

- variable_id (INT, FOREIGN KEY to Variables)
- repeated_variable_id (INT, PRIMARY KEY)